

Research Article

BENTIZ: BE-vezt

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Abstract: The idea of BENTIZ: BE-vezt was originally innovated from the main product called a beacon that builds inside a vest. This innovation was made for safety purposes and acts as an emergency solution for mariners and extreme enthusiasts. The reason is that one of the features, which is the button was built to be pressed by the users if they are in danger. The buttons that were built in the vest are connected to the beacon, so not only when the users intact with water, they can also use it on the land. Furthermore, the impacts from these products reduce the percentage of deaths and missing persons as the SAR team can send their team on the spot to the location of the victims. Once the vest is used, the beacon inside of it can be traded into a new product. Thus, this product was created to achieve SDG 11: "Sustainable Cities and Communities", and SDG 13: "Climate Action". With its practical, user-friendly, variety of size-fits-all design, it can be quickly repurposed as protective gear in water and on land. The product meets essential safety requirements while providing comfort and ease of use. As a result, it is indispensable for preventing not only mishaps but also fatalities in unsafe situations.

Keywords: Beacon, emergency, extreme activities, safety, vest

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1. INTRODUCTION

This innovation is primarily dedicated to the offshore workers who spend most of their time onboard and people who love to do extreme activities such as hiking, biking, and swimming. Offshore workers are placed as the top priority as they are constantly exposed to significant hazards including hazardous substances, noise, radiation, vibration, extreme temperature, and extreme weather

conditions (D’Antoine et al., 2023). One of the most recently reported accidents related to oil rigs involved the collision between the vessel, MV Dayang Topez and with Baram B oil platform, which is owned by Petronas Carigali. Out of 187 people onboard, 125 of them jumped overboard and were evacuated to Miri by the search and rescue (SAR) team, with two fatalities recorded (Krishnan, 2020).

The main component of this product, known as ‘beacon’, is built into a standard vest that is available in several types of colours and sizes. This small portable device works by sending out a distress signal to a global network satellite (Memon, 2022). The signal is then transmitted to the SAR team to locate the sender or victim. As for offshore workers, if they come into contact with water, such as a man in a man-overboard situation, the beacon will automatically detect their current location. Additionally, for extreme sports enthusiasts, there is a small button located on the upper left side of the vest which can be manually activated by the user. The vest itself is made from multiple layers, including a layer of calcium oxide that helps keep the user warm (HSE, 2024).

This vest is upgraded to an advanced version, making it more convenient and user-friendly combining several functions which make it different from normal vests that are being sold in the market. The safety purpose of this vest will help to reduce the percentage of deaths and missing persons as the SAR team can immediately send their team to the location of the victims (Perkins, 2015).

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

Figure 1. Features build in the BENTIZ: BE-vezt

Figure 2. Detail of each layer of BENTIZ: BE-vezt

Figure 3. Beacon Chip Layer

2.1 Procedure for using the BENTIZ: BE-vezt:

1. Wear the BENTIZ: BE-vezt as the first layer, underneath your offshore coverall or sports attire.
2. Ensure that both the beacon and vest are in good working condition.
3. **For Offshore Workers:**
In an emergency, if you are required to jump overboard, the beacon will automatically activate when the vest comes into contact with water. This will send a signal directly to the Search and Rescue (SAR) team.
4. **For Extreme Sports Enthusiasts:**
If you lose your way or are involved in an accident, you can manually activate the beacon by pressing the button located on the upper left side of the vest. If the button fails to function, an app connected to the beacon will automatically send the signal.
5. Once the vest contacts water, it will inflate to prevent drowning, and the calcium oxide lining will help keep you warm.

3. FINDINGS

The BENTIZ: BE-vezt is a stylish jacket that also functions as a life jacket, designed for versatility and safety. Data from a survey of 50 respondents shows a significant interest in the product. Notably, 42 respondents (84%) had previously used life jackets, suggesting that the target audience is already familiar with and inclined toward water safety products. What distinguishes the BENTIZ: BE-vezt is its combination of functionality and style. 45 respondents (89%) expressed their interest in a fashionable life vest, which demonstrates the product's appeal. In terms of usability, 41 out of 50 respondents (83%) confirmed that the BENTIZ: BE-vezt would be effective in extreme environments, highlighting its practical benefits. Additionally, 45 participants (89%) rated the vest as user-friendly.

Another key finding was that 48 respondents (96%) believed the product's features would be useful, indicating strong confidence in both its design and functionality especially the beacon which acts as the main device in this product. Importantly, 47 out of 50 respondents (95%) said they would recommend the BENTIZ: BE-vezt to their friends and family, which gives a strong potential for positive word-of-mouth promotion. This BENTIZ: BE-vezt has successfully combined safety, usability, and style factors that are highly valued by potential users. These findings suggest the product has strong market

potential, particularly among individuals involved in water-based mainly for offshore workers, and extreme sports activities.

4. DISCUSSION

In the case of man overboard, this beacon system would send an immediate alert to the search and rescue team, which would be very helpful to workers offshore. Water-activated upon contact, the beacon sends the location of the user to SAR personnel via satellite, even in places where cell service is not available. Moreover, the vest has a manually operated button which, in an emergency, sends out signals of distress for the extreme sports enthusiast. The sophisticated functionality of the vest is further exemplified by its ability to auto-inflate in contact with water and a lining made of calcium oxide that keeps the user warm. These features make the BENTIZ: BE-vezt a complete safety device. The study proceeds with the discussion of possible expansion in BENTIZ: BE-vezt by the addition of features such as real-time health monitoring, better GPS tracking, and increasing the life of the beacon battery.

The product line can be expanded to include items for the following high-risk professions: firefighters, military personnel, and SAR teams. It would also be very fundamental to the wider acceptance of BENTIZ: BE-vezt that it meets international safety standards on survival equipment and PFDs, at least for more regulated industries like offshore oil and gas. The novelty of the technology, BENTIZ: BE-vezt helps in enhancing safety in harsh environments for real-world benefit and market potential.

5. CONCLUSION

The study concluded that the BENTIZ: BE-vezt is a highly creative and well-designed multipurpose vest, specifically developed to meet the needs of offshore workers and to appeal to enthusiasts of extreme sports like jungle trekking, biking, or swimming. According to survey results, this solution is viable, performing well in terms of safety and comfort, with more than 93% of respondents expressing interest, and none recommending against its use. It includes an emergency feature that alerts rescuers to the victim's position and danger level.

This system consists of a manual emergency button (for those not on a boat) and a distress beacon with GPS that automatically activates once comes into contact with water. Additionally, the vest includes braille indicators, making it accessible for the visually impaired, and a calcium-oxide lining, enhancing its durability in moderate-to-aggressive outdoor environments. With its practical, user-friendly, variety of size-fits-all designs, it can be quickly repurposed as protective gear on land. The product meets essential safety requirements while providing comfort and ease of use. As a result, it is indispensable for preventing not only mishaps but also fatalities in unsafe situations.

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